

A Security-Friendly Privacy Preserving Solution for Federated Learning^{*}

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Abstract

Federated learning is a privacy-aware collaborative machine learning method where the clients collaborate on constructing a global model by performing local model training using their training data and sending the local model updates to the server. Although it enhances privacy by letting the clients collaborate without sharing their training data, it is still prone to the sophisticated privacy attacks because of possible information leakage from the local model updates sent to the server. To prevent such attacks, generally secure aggregation protocols are proposed so that the server will not be able to access the individual local model updates but the aggregated result. However, such secure aggregation approaches may not allow the execution of security mechanisms against some security attacks to model training, such as poisoning and backdoor attacks because the server cannot access the individual local model updates and; therefore, cannot analyze them to detect anomalies resulting from these attacks. Thus, solutions that satisfy privacy and security at the same time, or new privacy-preserving solutions that allow the server to execute some analysis on the local model updates without violating privacy are needed for federated learning. In this paper, we introduce a novel

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security-friendly privacy solution for federated learning based on multi-hop communication to hide clients' identities. Our solution ensures that the forwarder clients in the path between the source client and the server cannot execute malicious activities by altering model updates and contributing to the global model construction with more than one local model update in one FL round. We then propose two different approaches to make the solution also robust against possible malicious packet drop behaviors by the forwarder clients.

Keywords: Federated learning, privacy, security attacks, poisoning attacks, multi-hop communication

1. Introduction

The advances in artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) and foreseen increases in the amount of data, especially with the advent of 6G technologies, have brought advanced data-driven applications. The distributed nature of the data sources makes centralized aggregation and processing difficult due to the communication overheads. Another barrier to the full utilization of aggregated data is privacy concerns, e.g., accessing highly sensitive data such as medical records is often prohibited. Federated learning (FL) [2] is a privacy-aware mechanism to overcome these concerns, which generates the ML model jointly between the clients and a server. Each client trains on its own data, where local training results, so-called local model updates, are transferred to the server so that the training data never leaves the client. The server generates the global model by aggregating the local model updates. Although FL is a privacy-aware solution, there are still some other privacy and security concerns in the FL setting. First, the local model updates sent to the server may still disclose some information about the training data of the clients to the server [3]. Second, the participants (i.e., clients) in the FL setting are able to modify the local model updates to alter the global model maliciously such as performing poisoning attacks [4, 5]. A detailed analysis of security vulnerabilities and privacy threats in FL can be found in [6, 7]. To overcome the first concern, i.e., sensitive information disclosure, privacy-enhancing technologies (PETs) such as Homomorphic Encryption (HE), Secure Multi-party Computation, Differential Privacy (DP), and Confidential Computing have been proposed [8, 9, 10], which prevent the server from accessing the original local model updates in

cleartext so that the server cannot learn any information about the training data of the clients. Regarding the model-modifying concern, the server can analyze the local model updates to detect any suspicious behavior by clients. To address both concerns at the same time, PET-based solutions can also be utilized to allow the server to analyze local model updates without accessing them. However, employing these technologies may be costly, and there may be other trust assumptions and requirements, such as the need to have non-colluding servers. The other approach to overcome both concerns is to have privacy-enhanced solutions allowing the analysis of local model updates by the server without violating privacy. We will refer to this type of solution throughout this paper as a security-friendly privacy solution.

Related works. In the literature, several solutions to protect FL against both privacy and security attacks have been investigated. In one of the examples, MLGUARD [11], introduced in 2020, privacy of the clients is preserved by applying additive secret sharing on clients’ parameter updates, and the poisoning is mitigated by the servers computing a similarity score for each clients and rejecting the ones with the lowest similarity scores (most dissimilar). Another work FLGUARD [12], introduced in 2021, provides privacy for clients while protecting the FL process from multiple backdoor attacks. It requires two non-colluding servers and executes a secure two-party protocol to prevent backdoor attacks and meet the privacy requirements. Another approach [13] runs a secure aggregation protocol that is secure against malicious clients. The solution relies on the assumption that if a client or a group of clients wants to execute a backdoor attack, the model parameter updates of malicious clients diverge from those of legitimate clients. The proposed secure aggregation protocol detects these divergent points so that the server recognizes the presence of a backdoor attack. As another solution, Alberto et al. [14] propose anonymizing clients’ data using multi-hop communication between the clients and the server, as an adaptation of Domingo-Ferrer et al. multi-hop protocol [15]. The server receives local model updates in plaintext, enabling the server to analyze the updates and detect security attacks. At the same time, the server will not be able to know the client to which the data belongs. However, that solution has some drawbacks that need to be solved. For example, a malicious client can alter another client’s local model update and then send it to the server. Also, a malicious client can send multiple local model updates to be successful in its attack without being detected by the server. Another privacy-enhancing tool is the blind signature scheme that David Chaum introduced in 1982 [16], first employed for

untraceable payment applications. This scheme is a type of digital signature in which the content of the private data is disguised before being signed by a signature issuer (server). Since the issuer cannot obtain any information regarding the content of the data, the confidentiality of the data is guaranteed. One enhancement in the blind signature is the introduction of partially blind signatures [17, 18] where the issuer can input additional common information agreed upon by the client and issuer into the data before signing the data of the client. Partially blind signature schemes are widely used in electronic cash systems and electronic voting. Also, some other applications of partially blind signatures have also been introduced in the literature. For example, Gong et al. used partially blind signatures in smart grid applications [19]. Buccafurri et al. utilized partially blind signature in privacy-preserved analysis of social media “likes” [20]. Blind signatures found an application area in privacy preserving communication of VANETs in Fan et al. study [21]. Li et al. proposed a partially blind signature based technique for privacy-preserving of participatory sensing [22].

Our contribution. We extend our solution presented in [1] that improves the multi-hop communication solution proposed by Alberto et al. [14] using blind signatures to solve the problems of possible malicious behaviors of clients. We aim to solve the following malicious behaviors:

- Unauthorized modifications to the local model updates
- Sending multiple local model updates in one round of FL
- Dropping the local model updates of other clients

To detect unauthorized modifications to the local model updates in the multi-hop communication, the usage of signatures for the local model updates by the owner client is proposed. To address the other malicious behavior of sending multiple local model updates, we utilize partially blind signatures. The server provides signed public keys, to be used only once, to the clients blindly, and the clients will be able to use the corresponding private keys to sign local model updates. To prevent packet drops by compromised forwarder clients, we also introduce two alternative enhancements. The main contributions of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- We propose a privacy attack prevention technique that preserves the privacy of clients allowing them to use multi-hop communication instead of sending local model updates directly to the server.

- The proposed method enables the server to prevent malicious clients' local model updates from disturbing the global model.
- The proposed method enables the server to identify malicious behavior of the clients willing to alter the model updates or send multiple local model updates.
- The proposed enhancements prevent malicious forwarder clients from dropping local model updates of other clients.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 provides the preliminaries relating to the tools utilized in this paper. Section 3 discusses the proposed protocol. Section 4 presents experimental results about the performance of our protocol. Section 5 includes proposed enhancements on top of our protocol for preventing packet drops, and Section 6 concludes the paper.

2. Preliminaries

2.1. Notation

Throughout the paper, the following notation is used. (pk_i, sk_i) denotes the public and private key pair of the i -th client. c is to represent the commuting function used in the blind signature. s' is the blind signature operation of the server using its private key. c' and s are the inverse of c and s' , respectively. n denotes the number of clients in the FL setting. m is the tolerable number of lost local model updates in each FL round. $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{F}\mathcal{E}\mathcal{D}}$ is the global model and δ_i^j denotes the local model update for user i at round j .

2.2. Federated Learning

FL is a privacy-friendly collaborative ML technique where model training is distributed among multiple clients. In this learning scenario, a server initializes a global model $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{F}\mathcal{E}\mathcal{D}}$ and sends it to n clients where all clients wish to train an ML model using their respective data D_i for $i = 1, \dots, n$. Each FL process has several rounds such that at each round t (or iteration) of the FL, each client trains on its local data D_i and share only local model updates δ_i^t with the server for iterative aggregation until a convergent global model $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{F}\mathcal{E}\mathcal{D}}$ is reached on the server. The accuracy of the $\mathcal{G}_{\mathcal{F}\mathcal{E}\mathcal{D}}$ should be very close to the conventional method where all data from clients are put together to train a model [23].

2.3. Blind Signatures

Blind signatures, introduced by David Chaum [16], allow one party to have a signature for its private data from a signature issuer without leaking any information about the data. Chaum proposed to use this approach for untraceable payments. The blind signature protocol works as follows:

1. The client computes $c(x)$ where x is the input for the signature and c is the commuting function that is only known by the client. Then the client sends $c(x)$ to the server.
2. The server computes the signature operation to have $s'(c(x))$ where s' is the signature operation including the private key of the server. Then server send $s'(c(x))$ to the client.
3. The client recovers $s'(x)$ which is the server's signature on x by computing $c'(s'(c(x)))$ where c' is the inverse of c and only known by the client.

The usage of this blind signature concept for an untraceable payment works as follows:

1. The payer chooses a random x , computes $c(x)$, and sends the result to the bank.
2. The bank signs it ($s'(c(x))$), debits the payer's account, and sends the signature result to the payer.
3. The payer recovers the signature $c'(s'(c(x))) = s'(x)$ and verifies the signature using s where s is the signature verification including the public key of the Bank.
4. The payer sends $s'(x)$ to a payee.
5. The payee sends $s'(x)$ to the bank.
6. The bank verifies the signature and if the verification is successful, then checks whether x has been used before. Since the bank blindly signs x in step 2, the bank will not be able to match the payer and payee; so, privacy will be satisfied. If x has been used before, the bank refuses the payment; otherwise, the bank credits the account of the payee.

Partially blind signatures were introduced in [17, 18] where the signature issuer can input additional common information such as date or other agreed information into the data before signing the data of the client. Various implementations of partially blind signature have been proposed by using different cryptographic primitives such as RSA, ECDSA, and bilinear pairings [24, 25, 26].

2.4. Partially Blind Signature Scheme of Abe and Okamoto

We give a brief description of the partially blind signature scheme introduced by Abe and Okamoto in [18], which we use in the proof of concept implementation of our solution. This scheme is based on the discrete logarithm problem and consists of three main algorithms: key generation, partially blind signature issuing and verification algorithms. It is expected that the signer and user concurred on common information (*info*) prior to the execution of the partially blind signature protocol. The signer having the parameters $(p, q, g, x, info)$ and the user having the parameters $(y = g^x, info, msg)$ execute the following steps where g is an element of order q in Z_p^* , x is the private key of the signer, *info* is the pre-agreed data to be included in the signature, *msg* is the message to be signed.

1. The signer first selects three uniformly random values (u, s, d) from Z_p^* . Then, it computes $z = F(info)$ where F is a hash function mapping an arbitrary string to the set generate by g in Z_p^* . The signer sends a and b to the user, where $a = g^u$ and $b = g^s z^d$.
2. The user selects four uniformly random values (t_1, t_2, t_3, t_4) from Z_p^* , computes $z = F(info)$, $\alpha = ag^{t_1} y^{t_2}$, $\beta = bg^{t_3} z^{t_4}$, $\varepsilon = H(\alpha || \beta || z || msg)$, $e = \varepsilon - t_2 - t_4 \pmod q$, where H is a hash function and $||$ denotes the concatenation operation. The user sends e to the signer.
3. The signer computes $c = e - d \pmod q$ and $r = u - cx \pmod q$, and then sends (r, c, s, d) to the user.
4. The user computes $(\rho, \omega, \sigma, \delta)$, which is the signature on *info* and *msg*, as follows. $\rho = r + t_1 \pmod q$, $\omega = c + t_2 \pmod q$, $\sigma = s + t_3 \pmod q$, and $\delta = d + t_4 \pmod q$.

The verification of the signature is just checking the equation:

$$\omega + \delta = H(g^\rho y^\omega || g^\sigma z^\delta || z || msg)$$

where $z = F(info)$. For more detailed definition, the reader can refer to the paper [18] where the scheme was introduced.

3. Our protocol

We build our protocol on top of the solution proposed by Alberto et al. [14], where the main idea is to anonymize the local model updates sent to the server. This privacy approach allows the server to analyze the incoming data

to detect any poison or backdoor attack attempts. One of the drawbacks of the solution is the following. Since there is no data source authentication, malicious clients in the path between legitimate clients and server may utilize this anonymization technique to execute some attacks by modifying other clients' local model updates before forwarding them. Another threat by the malicious clients is to send multiple local model updates in one round of FL to alter the global model in their pursuit without being detected by the server. To prevent the clients from sending more than one local model update, we utilize cryptographic signatures for the source authentication. Not to break anonymity, we need to ensure that the server should not be able to learn the identities of the clients from the signatures. To address this requirement, we use blind signatures. The example interactions between the server and clients are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Example interactions between server and clients

In our trust model, we consider the server to be a malicious party that may want to learn about clients' training data. The clients are considered to be malicious parties who may try to alter the local model updates received from other clients, send multiple local model updates for one round of FL, or may want to learn information about the training data of other clients. The general idea in our protocol is that the server signs public keys for the clients blindly, so that the server should not learn the public keys of the clients while signing them. Also, to bind the public keys to a specific FL round, the server includes the current FL round number in the signature. To be able to insert this common information into the signature, we utilize partially blind signatures. For that purpose, the server signs the public keys sent by the

clients blindly. This operation is repeated for each round of FL. With this blind public key signing operation, the server ensures that it provides only one public key per client for each FL round. Before sending the local model update, each client signs its own update, and then the server validates the signature on the public keys and the signature on the local model updates. The server also stores the used public keys in a table to ensure that the public key is used only once. Thus, this solution allows the server to ensure that the clients in the setting have only one public key per FL round and also ensure that the clients can use the public keys to sign only one local model update. It is important for the clients to check that they have the same public key of the server where the public key is the corresponding private key used in the blind signature. With this check, the clients ensure that they cannot be tracked by the server since the secret key stays the same throughout the protocol for each of them. Otherwise, the server may try to violate the privacy of clients. We remark that the communication between the clients and server needs to be secured using confidentiality, integrity and authentication methods to ensure that the clients and the server are legitimate entities and the model is not revealed to anyone who is not in the FL setting such as man-in-the-middle attackers. The steps of our protocol, which are executed in each FL round, are as follows.

1. Each client generates a public-private key pair (pk_i and sk_i for the i -th client)
2. Each client runs a partially blind signature protocol with the server to have blindly signed public key (pk_i). Here the common information included in the partially blind signature is the current FL round number. $s'(pk_i, r_j)$ denotes the blindly signed public key where r_j is the current FL round number.
3. Then each client performs local training to obtain the local model update.
4. Each client signs the local model update using sk_i . Also, selects a random hop-counter and sends $pk_i, r_j, s'(pk_i, r_j)$, the local model update and its signature, and the hop-counter to a randomly selected forwarder.
5. Each client who receives a packet decreases the hop-counter in the received packet. The forwarder sends the received $pk_i, r_j, s'(pk_i, r_j)$, the signature of the local model update, the local model update, and the hop counter to the server or to another client.

6. The server executes the following steps when it receives a packet.
 - (a) Checks whether pk_i is used before for the r_j -th round.
 - (b) Verifies $s'(pk_i, r_j)$.
 - (c) Verifies the signature on the local model update using the received public key pk_i .
7. The server proceeds to the aggregation operation as long as it receives at least $n - m$ data packets that pass the checks in step 6. Thus, it is ensured that the FL is not disrupted if a client does not forward the model updates for malicious reasons, i.e., denial-of-service by malicious clients is somewhat reduced. Here, the parameter m can be calculated considering the probability of receiving m packets by the malicious client, using the number of clients and hop counts. Note that the server can also execute some analysis on the received local model updates to detect any poisoning attacks.

Security arguments. Our protocol aims to achieve the security requirements listed below. We also give sketched security arguments to show that our protocol meets these requirements.

1. *The server should not be able to learn the owner of the local model update.* Since the local model updates are sent to the server in a multi-hop communication, the server will not be able to learn the source client. The other way for the server to cheat is that the server can behave maliciously in the partially blind signature operation. Since we assume that the partially blind signature protocol is secure, the only way for the server is to use different keys for the blind signature operation to detect which public key belongs to which client, but the clients will detect this attempt because they check that the public key of the server is same for all clients.
2. *The server will be able to make some analysis on the local model updates to detect security attacks to the model training.* Since the local model updates are sent in cleartext to the server, the server will be able to execute some protection mechanisms against security attacks by analyzing received local model updates.
3. *Forwarder clients should not be able to learn the owner of the local model update received from a client.* Since the owner of the local model update includes a random hop counter to the packet sent to the forwarder client, the forwarder client will not be able to know whether the sender is the owner of the local model update.

4. *Forwarder clients should not be able to alter the local model update received from a client.* This is achieved with the usage of signatures on local model updates.
5. *Clients should not be able to send multiple local model updates to the server.* This is ensured as the server provides only one signed public key to each client for each FL round and checks whether the received public key has been used before.
6. *No one except the clients in the setting will be able to send local model updates to the server.* This is guaranteed since the server accepts local model updates from the clients whose public keys are blindly signed by the server. The server checks the server signature on the public key used to sign the local model update.

Performance considerations. We discuss the overheads of our protocol. The clients need different key pairs for each FL round. The cost of generating key pairs can be eliminated by generating them offline. The other additional step is the blind signature and model signature operations. Thus, the server needs to compute n blind signatures in step 2, and in step 6 needs to compute n blind signature verifications along with n normal signature verifications. For the clients, the computational overhead is the computation of one blind signature-related operation in Step 2 and the local model signature operation in Step 4. For the communication, each client needs to connect to the server to have blindly signed public keys. Also, the signed local model updates need to be sent hop-by-hop instead of directly sent to the server, which may cause some delay in the FL process, but this does not bring considerable computation overhead to the forwarder clients.

4. Experimental results

To evaluate the computation overhead brought by our protocol on the FL, we implemented our protocol using python and run the implementation on a standard user laptop with Intel Core i5 CPU and 32 GB RAM. For partially blind signature, we used the python implementation ² of the partially blind signature scheme of Abe and Okamoto, introduced in [18]. For 112-bit security, we preferred (2048-bit,224-bit) as the lengths of DSA parameters. We simulated the clients and the server as functions which are called sequentially

²<https://github.com/cowlicks/partially/blob/master/partially.py>

in a single execution thread. We first run an example FL with 20 clients and observed that local model training for each client takes time of 7 seconds in average, and the local model update size is around 4 MB. Taking the local model size into account, we evaluated the computation time of our protocol except the local training part. When we run our protocol, we observed that one partially blind signature operation requires 90 ms in total at the client and server side. The other dominant operation in terms of computation time is the signature operation by each client. This signature operation required 10 ms. The last dominant operation, which is done by the server, to validate the signatures on the local model updates and the public key of the clients took 25 ms. Thus, the computation overhead of our protocol is 125 ms in total for the operation done by the client and server. Considering that the local model training takes 7 seconds (7000 ms) for each client, the overhead of our protocol is negligible (1.8% increase in execution time).

The other consideration is about the communication cost overhead resulted from sending extra messages for the execution of our protocol. When we consider only sending local model updates having 4 MB size by the client to the server, it takes 61 ms in a network with the bandwidth of 1 Gbps and RTT (round trip time) of 1 ms parameters. When the network parameters are bandwidth of 6100 ms and RTT of 100 ms, the transfer of local model update requires 6100 ms. Considering that the required time for local model training is 7 seconds, it can be observed that the communication time is also another dominant time consumption in the networks where the bandwidth and RTT is not so good. Luckily, when the client and server has a better communication service, the communication time becomes negligible when compared to the computation time. Our protocol requires some additional parameters to be sent in addition to the local model update but the total lengths of these parameters are so small when compared to the local model update size. Thus in terms of additional parameters, our protocol does not bring considerable overhead. However, since our solution is based on multi-hop communication, a local model update needs to be send many times in the network instead of directly sent to the server. In the network setting with low bandwidth and high RTT, this multi-hop communication requirement brings considerable communication delay, but this can be disregarded in the better network settings. We can conclude that for the network settings having better parameters in terms of bandwidth and RTT, our solution becomes more promising. Figure 2 visualizes this conclusion showing that the overhead of our solution becomes negligible when the communication speed

Figure 2: Overhead of our solution depending on the communication speed. In the estimation of communication cost of our solution, the average number of hops for transfer of one local model update from the source client to the server is taken as 10.

becomes better.

5. Enhancing Our Protocol

Our main protocol introduced in Section 3 does not provide a solution for packet dropping by malicious clients. To make our solution resistant to such kind of malicious attempts, we introduce a new entity called the detector who monitors packet transferring procedure and detects when there is any failure. Depending on whether the detector should be online or offline, we propose two alternative enhancements.

Note that in the solution it is assumed that the detector and the server do not collude. The detector does not get the local model update packets however knows all the traffic flow by observing the messages from forwarder and receiver clients. Other clients and the server are not aware of this traffic since detector would not share this information.

The protocol in Section 3 can solve the problem of packet drops by malicious clients by setting $m = 0$ where m is the tolerable local model update loss. In this case, the server will wait to receive packets from all the clients

in each FL round. A client will be able to send only one packet due to the usage of blind signature. Since server waits n packets, a packet drop by a malicious client will halt the execution of the FL round and the server will restart the FL round after a predefined time period. However, setting $m = 0$ allows malicious clients to execute a DoS attack because dropping at least one packet will lead the server to wait for n packets and restart the round because of missing packets. Thus, m can be tuned considering the number of packets allowed to be dropped and the possibility of DoS attacks. With this enhanced solution, m can be chosen as 0 safely because when a malicious client drops a packet, it will be detected by the detector and the client will be excluded from the setting. But if the malicious client computes its local model signature illegitimately, then the client may prevent execution of FL if $m = 0$. To prevent this DoS attack, m can be tuned considering possible number of malicious clients.

5.1. Online Detector

In this solution, when a sender client sends a packet including a local model update to a forwarder client, it also sends a message to the detector to inform the detector about the packet the transfer. To uniquely determine the packet, the data sent to the detector by the sender client includes hash of the packet, sender client id and the forwarder client id. Accordingly, whenever a forwarder client receives a packet, it sends a message to the detector with the same information, forwarder and sender client IDs and hash of the packet, to inform a packet has been received. Then the detector checks the messages and if they match, it sends an acknowledgment packet to the sender client which means the packet transmission has been completed successfully. By this way, the detector tracks the information attached to the message to ensure there's no packet drop. Otherwise, if sender client does not get an acknowledgment message from the detector, sender client executes same steps for another randomly chosen forwarder client. Figure 3 visualizes such as flow for local model update packet of client 1.

The additions to the steps of our main protocol presented in Section 3 are given as follows.

- Additions to Step 4. Each client sends messages to the detector, including sender client id, forwarder client id and hash of the concatenation of sender client public key, round-no, server's signature on the public key and round-no, local model signature, the local model (SC_ID ,

Figure 3: Example interactions between Server, Clients and Detector. Note that only the packet flow for Client1 data is shown as an example.

$FC_ID, \text{Hash}(PubKey_i, round-no, S_i, SC_i, U_i)$. The client waits for an acknowledgment message, $SC_ID, FC_ID, \text{Hash}(PubKey_i, round-no, S_i, SC_i, U_i)$ from detector and if the detector has not sent the aforementioned ack message, then the client randomly chooses another client and sends the same packet.

- Additions to Step 5. After receiving a packet from a client, the forwarder sends a message to the detector to acknowledge that the packet has been received. The message includes sender client id, forwarder client id and hash of the concatenation of the following parameters in the received packet: public key, $round-no$, server's signature on the public key and $round-no$, local model signature, the local model ($SC_ID, FC_ID, \text{Hash}(PubKey_i, round-no, \xi_{i,i}, i)$). By this way, the detector ensures the sender client has sent the packet and forwarder client has received the packet by comparing this message with the message received from the sender client. Then the detector creates an acknowledgement message for sender client including acknowledgement, sender and receiver client ids and the hash received from the forwarder client. When the forwarder client sends the packet to the server or to another forwarder, the client sends a message including its client id, the server ID or the next forwarder client id and hash of the concatenation the following parameters in the received packet: public

key, round-no, server’s signature on the public key and round-no, local model signature, the local model (FC_ID, SC_ID or next FC_ID, $\text{Hash}(\text{PubKey}_i, \text{round-no}, S_i, SC_i, U_i)$), to the detector. The client waits for corresponding acknowledgement message from the detector. If the client does not get an ack message, then it chooses randomly another forwarder client and sends the same packet.

- Additions to Step 6. The server sends a message to the detector as other clients when a packet has been received by the sender. Thus, the detector will ensure the packet reached its destination finally.
- Additions to Step 7. The server waits at least $n-m$ data packets that pass the checks in step 6 where n is the number of clients and $n - m$ is the number of clients required in the computation of the update of the global model. If that number is reached in the predefined time period, then the next round starts with step 1. The reason why we set a number m is as follow: This solution allows execution of FL when at most m local model updates can be computed illegitimately by the m malicious clients who may want to prevent execution of FL.

Performance considerations. Ensuring whether a local model update has been sent to the destination brings some additional cost in terms of communication. For sending the local model update to the next hop, this enhancement requires four additional communication rounds in total between the sender, receiver and the detector. Also, the sender and receiver execute hash function computation not to allow the detector to see the content of the local model updates and also to shorten the data length in these additional rounds. Since the hash function computation cost is negligible compared to the local model training, and the cost of sending the short messages are negligible compared to the cost of sending local model updates, the overhead of this enhancement can be disregarded.

5.2. Offline Detector

This enhancement solution doesn’t require the detector to be online. Here the clients collect signed acknowledgments (ack) about receiving packets and then send the ack packets to the detector. Also the server reports the received valid packets to the detector. At the end of the FL round or FL process, the detector performs an analysis to detect if there is any client who didn’t send

a received packet to the next hop. The additions to the steps of the protocol presented in Section 3 are given as follows.

- Additions to Step 4. The client waits for a signed acknowledgment message consisting of sender client id, forwarder client id and hash of the local model update packet. If the client does not receive an ack packet then it randomly chooses another client and sends the same local model update packet.
- Additions to Step 5. After receiving a local model update packet, the forwarder client sends a signed acknowledgment message to the previous forwarder client in the communication path to acknowledge that the packet has been received. The acknowledgment packet is a signed packet by the forwarder client, where the signature is computed on local model update packet. When the forwarder client sends the packet to the server or to another forwarder, the client waits for a signed ack message from the server or the forwarder client. If the client does not get an ack message, then it chooses randomly another forwarder client and sends the same packet.
- Additions to Step 6. The server sends a signed acknowledgment message to the forwarder client, who is the last forwarder client in the communication path and has sent the packet to the server, to acknowledge that the packet has been received.
- A new step. Each client/forwarder sends the received signed ack messages to the Detector. Note that sending the ack messages can be done at the end of each FL round, or the clients send the ack messages to the Detector after receiving these messages. The detector analyzes the received ack messages to decide whether there was any anomaly/malicious behavior during the packet transfers in FL round. For example, the Detector executes the following check for each client. Detector compares the ack packets sent by that client and the ack packets received by that client. When the ack packets are matched, there should be only one ack packet left which was received by that client for its own local model update.

Performance considerations. Similar to the previous enhancement solution, the overhead of this enhancement is negligible because of very small costs

resulted from computation of signatures and sending short messages when compared to the our main protocol. The extra operations to realize this enhancement is computation of signatures by the receiver for ack messages and sending these ack messages to the sender. In the end of the protocol, the sender also sends the received ack messages to the detector.

6. Conclusion

The adoption of collaborative ML/AI, especially FL, will increase in future generation networks to address distributed nature of data analytic and computations stemming from emerging use cases such as internet of senses and extended reality. It is important to provide trustworthy methodologies for FL. With this motivation, we propose a new method to improve security and privacy in FL. Our method is based on a new approach that uses partially blind signatures to resolve residual privacy and security issues of the multi-hop communication approach for anonymization of clients participating in the FL training, suggested in [14]. Our approach mitigates the possible malicious behaviors of clients. We consider two types of malicious behavior (i) unauthorized modifications to the local model update during transmission to the server (ii) sending multiple local model updates to the server. We address the first one by introducing signatures for the local model updates by the owner client and the second one by using partially blind signatures where the server provides one usage signed public key to the clients blindly, and the clients use the public keys to sign local model updates only once. We also propose two enhancements for our main solution to make it robust against packet drops by compromised forwarder clients. To the best of our knowledge, our solution is the first solution that uses partially blind signatures in the FL setting.

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